

K-12 PROGRAM: ISSUES AND CONCERNS OF PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract: This study determined the K-12 Program Issues and Concerns of Public Elementary School Teachers of Maluso East District, Basilan Schools Division. The subject of the study were the teachers in 11 Public Elementary Schools in Maluso East District, Basilan schools Divisions. A stratified random sampling procedure was employed in the selection of the respondents of the study. The descriptive research design was adopted in this study. A two - part survey questionnaire was used. Part one drew information about: the socio-demographic profile of the teachers, which includes: Age, Sex, Civil Status; Ethnicity; Educational Attainment; and Length of Service/Experience. Part two of the questionnaire determined the K-12 Program Issues and Concerns of Public Elementary School Teachers in Maluso East District, Basilan Schools Division. These were in the areas of: Content; Goals and Objectives; Social Environment; Teaching and Learning Process; Plans and Activities; Evaluation; and Physical Facilities. The finding of the study is that, the K-12 Program Issues and Concerns of the teachers were greatest in the area of Teaching and Learning Process, followed by Issues and Concerns in the areas of Goals and Objectives; Social Environment, Evaluation, and Plans and Activities.

Keywords: Basilan; Descriptive Research Design; Evaluation; Goals and Objectives; Issues and Concerns; Physical Facilities; Plans and Activities; Public Elementary School Teachers; Social Environment; Teaching and Learning Process.

I. INTRODUCTION

In pursuance of section 16 of Republic Act No. 10533, entitled "An Act Enhancing the Philippine Basic Education System by Strengthening Its Curriculum and Increasing the Number of Years for Basic Education, Appropriating Funds Thereof and for Other Purposes, otherwise known. as the "Enhanced Basic Education act of 2013", which was approved on May 15, 2013, the Department of Education, marking a milestone in the Philippine educational system, implements the K-12 program.

According to the K to 12 DepEd Primer (2011), "K-12 means "Kindergarten and the 12 years of elementary and secondary education." Kindergarten points to the 5-year-old child who undertakes the standardized curriculum for preschoolers. Elementary education refers to 6 years of primary school (Grades 1-6) while secondary education means four years of junior high school (Grades 7-10 or HS Year 1-4). In addition to this, two years are now allotted for senior high school (Grades 11-12 or HS Year 5-6).

Teachers are key to the successful implementation of new curricula, as they are the means used to turn innovations into classroom realities (Pinto et al., 2007). Teachers are expected to adopt the new ideas and implement them in their teaching

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i.e. change in curriculum requires change in teachers' practices (Fullan, 1992). These demands put strain on teachers as it requires them to change their practice and resume the role of "novice" again (Fogleman, J., McNeill, K. L., & Krajcik, J., 2011).

Kennedy (1996) stated that, "those having to implement the educational changes taking place are the teachers within the public education system who are having to adopt new ideologies and implement them in their teaching, since it is the teachers who are responsible for passing on the changes through their teaching to 'their students (i.e. the future citizens the governments are concerned to educate). This double demand (teachers having to change their teaching ideologies and then pass on those ideologies through their teaching to their students who also have to change) puts teachers under strain where the changes involved represent a major shift in beliefs and practices, and can threaten successful implementation unless necessary logistical and professional conditions are met." School resources should include: teachers, learners, parents, knowledge, and time.

When teachers interact with the innovation they may accept, reject or modify some parts to make it suit their particular context. The innovations get transformed in the process, as "the new and old overlap to create a zone of turbulence and challenge" (Pinto et al., 2007). Problems manifest themselves in the gaps between the intended curriculum (as expressed in policy document), the implemented curriculum (expressed by real life in schools and classroom practices), and the attained curriculum as expressed by learners' experiences (Fogleman, J., McNeill, K. L., & Krajcik, J., 2011). Various studies have been conducted focusing on the 'problems' of teachers regarding the K-12 curriculum implementation.

In Maluso East District, Basilan School Division, the public elementary school teachers, being the frontline implementers of the K-12 program, are faced with the difficulties related to the enormous task of successfully implementing the program. An insight on these K-12 Program issues and concerns of the teachers, being the most potent resources in the teaching-learning process, is needed to successfully implement the program.

It is based on the premises presented that there is a need to determine the K-12 Program Issues and Concerns of Public Elementary School Teachers of Maluso East District, Basilan Schools Division, and serving as basis, enhance the teaching-learning processes in schools in the district.

II. BODY OF ARTICLE**STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM**

This study was conducted to determine the K-12 Program Issues and Concerns of Public Elementary School Teachers of Maluso East District, Basilan Schools Division. It sought to answer the question:

What are the K-12 Program Issues and Concerns of Public Elementary School Teachers of Maluso East District, Basilan Schools Division, K-12 Program in the areas of:

- a. Content;
- b. Goals and Objectives;
- c. Social Environment;
- d. Teaching and Learning Process;
- e. Plans and Activities;
- f. Evaluation; and
- g. Physical Facilities?

THE RESEARCH METHOD

This study sought to determine the 'K-12 Program Issues and Concerns of the Public Elementary School Teachers in Maluso East District, Basilan Schools Division'. In describing the nature of the situation, as it exists at the time of the study, the descriptive method was appropriate to use. Thus, this study used the descriptive research design.

THE RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

When information is desired, a questionnaire is used when it gives an opportunity for establishing rapport, explaining the purpose of the study, and explaining the meaning of items (Best and Kahn, 1998). A two-part survey questionnaire was used in this study.

Part one drew information about: the socio-demographic profile of the teachers, which includes: Age, Sex, Civil Status; Ethnicity; Educational Attainment; and Length of Service/Experience.

Part two of the questionnaire determined the K-12 Program Issues and Concerns of Public Elementary School Teachers in Maluso East District, Basilan Schools Division. These were in the areas of: Content; Goals and Objectives; Social Environment; Teaching and Learning Process; Plans and Activities; Evaluation; and Physical Facilities.

THE VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY OF THE INSTRUMENT

Since the instrument adopted is the instrument developed by Erden (2010), which validity had already been established, then there was no need to subject it to a validation process.

A pre-testing of the questionnaire was conducted on Thirty (30) public elementary school teachers from the other school districts in Basilan-ARMM Schools Division, who were not included in the study. An instrument reliability analysis conducted on the pre-test data produced a Cronbach Alpha value of 0.8311, which would reflect that the reliability of the instrument was 'Very Good'.

STATISTICAL TREATMENT OF DATA

To determine the extents to which teachers are affected by the K-12 PROGRAM Issues & Concerns, the Weighted Mean, and Ranking were used.

III. THE K-12 PROGRAM ISSUES AND CONCERNS OF THE TEACHERS

Table 1 shows the summary of the weighted mean, description, and ranking on the K-12 Program Issues and Concerns of Public Elementary Schools Teachers in Maluso East District, Basilan Schools Division, in the areas of: Content; Goals and Objectives; Social Environment; Teaching and Learning Process; Plans and Activities; Evaluation; and Physical Facilities.

Table 1: Summary Of Weighted Means, Descriptions, And Rankings on The 'K-12Program Issues and Concerns' Of The Teachers In All Areas

AREA	MEAN	DESCRIPTION	RANK
A. Content	3.290	Moderate Extent	6
B. Goals and Objectives	3.535	Great Extent	2
C. Social Environment	3.516	Great Extent	3
D. Teaching and Learning Process	3.572	Great Extent	1
E. Plans and Activities	3.414	Great Extent	5
F. Evaluation	3.483	Great Extent	4
G. Physical Facilities	3.181	Moderate Extent	7
OVERALL	3.433	Great Extent	NA

The K-12 Program Issues and Concerns of the teachers were greatest in the area of Teaching and Learning Process (Great Extent), followed by Issues and Concerns in the areas of Goals and Objectives; Social Environment, Evaluation, and Plans and Activities (Great Extents).

The K-12 Program Issues and Concerns were lesser in the area of Physical Facilities (Moderate Extent), followed by Content (Moderate Extent).

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Overall, the K-12 Program Issues and Concerns of the teachers were to 'Great Extents'.

The K-12 Program Issues and Concerns of the teachers were mostly, as ranked:

1. Encouraging children to involve in activities based on cooperation (Teaching and Learning Process).
2. Encouraging children's active involvement (Teaching and Learning Process)
3. Respecting individual differences (Teaching and Learning Process)
4. Establishing good relations with school head/principal (Social Environment)
5. Establishing good relations with colleagues (Social Environment)
6. Evaluating child (Evaluation)
7. Using appropriate teaching methods and techniques (Teaching and Learning Process)
8. Learner centered process planning (Teaching and Learning Process)
9. Preparing daily activities plans (Plans and Activities)
10. Designing reading and writing practices (Plans and Activities)

The list could be considered as the bigger problems encountered by the teachers in their implementation of the K-12 curriculum.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, the hypothesis that the extents of the K 12 Program 'Issues and Concerns' of the Public Elementary School Teachers of Maluso East District, Basilan Schools Division are moderate, is rejected, on the basis that the K-12 Program Issues and Concerns of the teachers were to 'Great Extents'.

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